

SPARK PLASMA SINTERING OF GLASS MICROSPHERES WITH YAG COMPOSITION

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ABSTRACT

The work deals with the preparation of bulk glass with yttrium aluminium garnet (YAG) composition from glass microspheres prepared by flame synthesis. Viscous flow sintering of the microspheres was performed to prepare bulk glass in a SPS. Dense translucent YAG glass were successfully prepared at temperatures below 950°C without isothermal heating.

Glass microspheres with YAG composition were prepared according to process described elsewhere [1]. Dense YAG glass and glass/ceramic samples were prepared by SPS (spark plasma sintering technique Dr Sinter SPS-625 from Fuji Electronic Industrial CO., LTD.). Carbon foil (0.5 mm thick) cladged graphite dies were filled with prepared YAG glass microspheres and sintered under vacuum at different conditions (see Tab. 1).

Table 1.: Summary of SPS sintering conditions and dilatation of the samples.

Sample	Pressure [MPa]	Heating rate [°C/min]	Dilatation of sample [mm]	max T [°C]
SPS 921	60	50	1.91	902.1
SPS 922	70	50	2.02	898.9
SPS 924	80	50	2.28	904.1

The density of sintered samples was measured by Archimedes' method in water.

The phase composition of sintered samples was determined by X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) using a Panalytical Empyrean DY1098 diffractometer, operated at 40 kV and 45 mA with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.15405$ nm). The data were acquired over a 2θ range of 10-80° (step size 0.01°, 50 s/step). The data were evaluated using the High Score Plus software with the crystallographic open database (COD 2018).

The XRD analysis of SPS sintered samples at different uniaxial pressures (60, 70 and 80 MPa) revealed that all samples are XRD amorphous. Hence, the densification temperature was set below the onset of the crystallization temperature. The shrinkage of the samples mentioned in Tab. 1 together with XRD analysis leads towards the conclusion that the densification was successfully done by viscous-flow sintering.

Fig. 1. XRD patterns of glasses with YAG composition SPS densified at different pressures.

Additionally, Fig. 2 presents the photography of prepared translucent YAG glass/ceramic samples with diameter of 12 mm placed directly on the text. The translucency was achieved in two cases: (a) at the pressure of 60 MPa and temperature 902 °C and (c) 80 MPa and temperature 904 °C. Opacity in the sample shown in Fig. 2 (b) was ascribed to the lower densification temperature 899 °C compare to the 902 °C used in the (a) case despite of the fact that higher pressure of 70 MPa to the 60 MPa between the (b) and (a) trials, was applied.

Fig. 2: The photograph of the prepared translucent YAG glass/ceramic with diameter 12 mm placed on the text. Pressure used during densification a) 60 MPa; b) 70 MPa; c) 80 MPa.

This work describes successful preparation of translucent glass with YAG composition at temperatures below 950 °C without dopants widening the kinetic window. Lower temperature leads to opaque white sample while increasing of the densification temperature resulted in translucent samples.

Keywords: flame synthesis, microspheres, SPS, YAG

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References:

[1] Chovanec, J.; Svoboda, R.; Kraxner, J.; Černá, A.; Galusek, D. Crystallization kinetics of the $Y_3Al_5O_{12}$ glass. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* 725 [25] (2017), pp. 792-799.